

material with a diam of 6-8 mm. It costs the same as PU to produce and apply. Its size makes it ideal for broadcast application.

We compared the performance of LGU, RPCU, USG, and PU at eight sites, each with four on-farm trials, during the 1988 and 1989 kharif (Apr-May to Sep-Oct) and rabi (Sep-Oct to Dec-Jan) seasons. Soil texture varies from clayey loam to loam, pH 5.1-5.4, specific conductance 0.08-0.12 dS/m. 1.0-1.05% organic C, 5.0-6.5 kg available P/ha, and 125-170 kg available K/ha. All plots received 45 kg P and K/ha. P was applied basal and K in two splits: half basal and half at tillering. Jyothy was the test variety.

Rice yielded more grain with modified urea materials than with PU at the same N level (see table). To

Effect of N source on grain yield. On-farm trials, Thrissur, Kerala, India, 1988 and 1989.

Treatment no. ^a	N level and source (kg n/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)					
		Kharif			Rabi		
		1988	1989	Pooled	1988	1989	Pooled
1. Control (no N)		2.8	2.9	2.9	2.9	3.1	2.9
2. 84 - PU		3.4	3.6	3.5	3.6	3.2	3.4
3. 84 - USG		3.6	3.8	3.7	3.9	3.4	3.7
4. 84 - LGU		3.9	3.8	3.8	4.0	3.4	3.7
5. 84 - RPCU		3.6	3.8	3.7	3.8	3.7	3.8
6. 84 - LGU		3.9	3.9	3.9	3.9	3.5	3.7
7. 112 - PU		3.9	3.8	3.8	3.7	3.3	3.5
8. 112 - LGU		4.1	3.8	3.9	4.1	3.5	3.8
	LSD (0.05)	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.3

^a 2 = 1/3 basal (B) + 1/3 at tillering (T) + 1/3 at panicle initiation (PI). 3 = full B: 4 = full B: 5 = full B: 6 = 1/2 B + 1/2 T: 7 = 1/3 B + 1/3 T + 1/3 PI: 8 = 1/2 B + 1/2 T: USG point placed at 5 cm depth, all other fertilizers were broadcast.

equal the yield produced with 84 kg N/ha as LGU, USG, or RPCU required 112 kg N/ha as PU. The extra yield makes LGU an efficient and economic

source of N. The nonsignificant difference between PU and LGU at 112 kg N/ha may be due to Jyothy's lack of response above 84 kg N/ha. □

Crop management

Effect of herbage cutting on deepwater rice (DWR) in acid sulfate soil

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Acid sulfate soil restricts rice growth, resulting in low biomass production and low grain yield. We assessed the effect of herbage cutting on rice herbage and grain yield in acid sulfate deepwater areas during 1988 and 1989 wet seasons.

Four farmers' fields—three with acid soils, one without—planted to different local DWR varieties were the experiment sites. At each location, two

treatments (control and cut) were arranged in a randomized complete block design with 10 replications. Rice was dry seeded onto plowed soil at 120 kg seeds/ha. No fertilizer or other chemicals were applied. Data on agronomic practices and water depth are in Table 1.

In the cut plot, leaves were removed at the collar level of the last fully developed

leaf once in 1988 trials and two times in 1989 trials.

Average herbage yields, dry weight basis, on acid sulfate soils ranged from 0.4 t/ha from one cutting in 1988 to 0.6 t/ha from double cutting in 1989 (Table 2). Nonacid sulfate soil areas in

Prachinburi and Ayutthaya produced more than 1 t/ha. Low rates of dry matter accumulation might be the cause

Table 1. Rice cultivars and agronomic practices in rice herbage experimental plots in acid sulfate deepwater areas of Prachinburi, Thailand.

Location	Year	Acid sulfate soil	Cultivar	Sowing date	Cutting date		Maximum water		Harvesting date
					First	Second	Depth (cm)	Date	
Bansang	1988	Yes	Khao Lopburi	4 Apr	15 Aug	-	70	15 Oct	19 Dec
Bansang	1989	Yes	Khao Lhong	7 Aug	10 Aug	10 Sep	125	10 Oct	22 Dec
Klongsong	1989	Yes	Khao Lhong	7 Aug	10 Aug	10 Sep	120	10 Oct	25 Dec
Muang	1989	No	Hawn Tawng	15 Apr	11 Aug	11 Sep	100	20 Sep	5 Dec

Table 2. Herbage yield, grain yield, and yield components of rice cultivars as affected by herbage cutting in acid sulfate deepwater areas of Prachinburi, Thailand.^a

Location	Year	Cultivar	Herbage yield (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)		Panicles/m ²		Spikelets/panicle		Fertility (%)		1000-grain wt (g)		Dry matter (t/ha)		Height (cm)	
				Control	Cut	Control	Cut	Control	Cut	Control	Cut	Control	Cut	Control	Cut	Control	Cut
Bansang	1988	Khao Lopburi	0.4	1.9	1.7	111	119	69	57	84	85	28.1	27.9	-	-	145	126
Bansang	1989	Khao Lhong	0.6	1.6	1.5	105	107	98	93	81	80	26.0	25.9	9.4	7.9	255	230
Klongsong	1989	Khao Lhong	0.5	2.0	1.8	87	91	93	89	89	88	25.9	26.0	10.6	9.1	245	235
Muang	1989	Hawn Tawng	1.1	2.2	2.1	120	125	98	89	79	81	26.7	27.0	15.0	13.7	255	242
Average			0.6	1.91	1.80	106	111	90	82	83	84	26.7	26.7	11.7	10.2	225	208

Differences in grain yield and yield components between control and cut plots were not statistically significant. Herbage removal significantly reduced dry matter and plant height,

of low herbage yields in acid sulfate areas. Herbage cutting did not significantly affect grain yield and yield components.

Plant height and dry matter production were significantly decreased by herbage removal. Fertilizer application

and increased cuttings may improve the relatively low herbage yield and make it more economical. □

Integrated pest management—diseases

Growth and sclerotial production of *Sclerotium oryzae* on different media

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S. oryzae was grown on 15 natural and synthetic media in petri plates to test their growth and production of sclerotia. Fungus colony diameters were measured after 5 d of incubation. Petri plates were further incubated to observe sclerotial production. The plates were examined every 5 h to study sclerotial characters.

Average growth was maximum on potato dextrose agar and minimum on Backman and Kabana's medium and Brown's agar (see table). All of the media except Backman and Kabana's medium and Neurospora V synthetic medium produced sclerotia.

The results showed no correlation among the radial growth of fungus, time of initiation, color, size, arrangement, and average number of sclerotia per plate. □

Effect of different media on growth and sclerotial production of *S. oryzae*.

Medium	Av colony diam ^a (mm)	Time until sclerotial initiation (h)	Arrangement of sclerotia	Color of sclerotia	Size of sclerotia ^b (µm)	Av sclerotia/plate (no.)
Backman and Kabana's medium	26.7	-	-	-	-	-
Brown's agar	26.7	170	More toward periphery, less toward center	Black	249.37	4875
Corn meal agar	50.7	120	More toward periphery, less toward center	Black	266	13455
Czapek-Dox agar	63.3	125	Equally scattered	Brownish black	248.90	17550
Dextrose marmite agar	46.7	170	Equally scattered	Shiny black	266	1346.5
Neurospora V synthetic medium	35.7	-	-	-	-	-
Nutrient glucose agar	51.3	125	Equally scattered	Black	274.86	40755.5
Oatmeal agar	65	145	More toward periphery, less toward center	Black	248.26	17225.5
Peptone sucrose agar	51.3	130	More toward periphery, less toward center	Black	248.30	41471.5
Potato carrot agar	46.7	120	Equally scattered	Shiny black	274.86	45882
Potato dextrose agar	73.3	120	Equally scattered	Shiny black	274.86	45882
Radish root extract agar	30	145	Equally scattered	Brownish black	268	23075
Rice polish agar	41.3	125	Equally scattered	Black	294.30	12490.5
Richard's agar	36.7	130	More toward periphery, less toward center	Black	248.90	21650
Sach's agar	35	125	Equally scattered	Black	230	12255.5

^aAfter 5 d, based on 3 replications. ^bAv of 100 sclerotia. ^cLSD value of average colony diam (mm) at 5% = 3.98. CV = 5.27.

Effect of humic acid (HA) on severity of rice blast (BI)

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We studied the effectiveness of graded levels of HA extracted from lignite on the severity of BI in rice varieties IR50 (highly susceptible) and IR20 (moderately resistant) under greenhouse conditions.

HA powder at the rate of 0, 10, 20, 30, and 40 kg/ha was dissolved in the required quantity of 0.01 N KOH to obtain pH 7.2. These solutions were then mixed thoroughly into pots that

Effect of humic acid level on B1 incidence.^a

HA level (kg/ha)	IR50			IR20		
	Mean disease incidence (%)	Angular transformed value	Decrease from control (%)	Mean disease incidence (%)	Angular transformed value	Decrease from control (%)
0	51.3	45.7	-	27.8	31.8	-
10	25.2	30.1	33.5	15.5	23.2	27.3
20	22.3	28.2	38.3	13.3	21.3	33.0
30	36.5	37.2	18.7	19.7	26.4	17.2
40	40.9	39.8	13.1	22.4	28.2	11.3

^aMean of 3 replications.

already had the recommended dose of fertilizer. Seedlings were transplanted; treatments were replicated three times.

At 50 d after sowing the plants were artificially inoculated with the B1 pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav.

Disease incidence was assessed using a score chart of 0-9.

HA application reduced B1 severity. Reduction was maximum with 20 kg/ha. □